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FAYOZTEPA - THE ROAD TO MAZI

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Annotation: *This article tells about the history of the ancient Fayoztepa monument, the secrets of the Buddhist temple and the conditions of its time.*

Surkhan oasis is a historical place with ancient monuments. Open-air historical monuments such as Kampirtepa, Zartepa, Fayoztepa are among them. Each monument is a mystery of history, rich in its own mysteries and wonderful realities. Located in the northwest of the ruins of the old city of Termez near the city of Termez, 1 km northeast of Qoratepa, between the banks of the Amudarya and the ancient caravan route, Fayoztepa is an ancient complex that speaks of the wonders of the maze. Fayoztepa is a Buddhist monastery built in the 1st-3rd centuries AD and is one of the oldest buildings in Uzbekistan. The temple began to fall into disrepair in the ninth century and was eventually reduced to rubble.

The total area of the complex is about 1.5 thousand square meters. Fayoztepa area was discovered in 1968-1976 by archaeologist L.I. Albaum. studied by In 1968, a statue of Buddha was found in the area. The walls of the monument are mainly made of cotton and brick, especially the walls of the Monastery and the Temple are up to 3 m high. All the walls are plastered with straw mud, and in many cases the plaster is whitewashed and the top is decorated with a colorful picture. One of the main components of the temple is STUPA, which, unlike other temples, is located not inside but outside, in a line parallel to the sacred shrine.

There is a statue of Buddha in the sacred shrine of the temple, and the walls of the shrine are decorated with colorful murals. Underneath the walls are red statues of Buddha with golden water. On the south wall of the shrine is an image of the Buddha in a red robe. On both sides of it are pictures of two men in long dresses with shoulder pads. One of them is depicted worshiping the Buddha. The plaster pieces in the room depict different people. A piece of plaster measuring 60x80 cm found a picture of two men facing the Buddha. In both forms, the Bactrian Buddhists are depicted as worshiping the Buddha.

Among the statues in the Fayoztepa temple, the head of the Buddha, made of clay, attracts attention.

Her curly black hair and beautiful face give her beauty. This was the first encounter of the Buddha in a Kushan monument. Two Kanishka and one Vasudeva coins and a unique work of art made of marble were found in the shrine. The Buddha, wrapped in a triad-silk mantle, sits under the arch and the branches of the sacred bodha tree, and the monks standing on either side of him are depicted praying to him. The temple courtyard of the complex covers an area of 33x20mt and is rectangular in shape. On all four sides of the courtyard, the monks had rooms with doors facing the courtyard. The temple is surrounded by a long porch along the walls. The fact that the walls of the porch are decorated with colorful murals can be seen from the fragments of paintings that have survived only at the bottom.

There was a courtyard in the center of the temple. He gave the building elegance and uniqueness, as the walls of the courtyard were filled with columns and embossed paintings. In the middle of the courtyard, a trinity seal was found depicting a Buddha sitting peacefully and spiritually in harmony under a sacred bodha tree. The whole composition has become a symbol of divinity, peace and tranquility. The trinity seal is the most valuable find and is kept in the State Museum of History of Uzbekistan, a copy of which can be seen in the Termez Archaeological Museum. To the northwest of the temple courtyard is a trapezoidal pool made of marble fragments, with a hole in the base in the shape of a lion's head with wide open jaws for draining water. In such pools, the water was kept clean and used for consumption.

The image of the lion is reflected in the art of the Kushan period as a symbol of the power of the Buddha. The second part of the religious complex is the Monastery, which is connected to the temple by an open door from the courtyard walls. The rooms on the monastery square were inhabited by monks and students of the monastery, the monastery has dormitories for pilgrims, schools for students and halls. On the walls of the room are shelves for wicker lamps. To the south-east of the temple is its farm, which covers a square area of 34.5x33.5mt. Fifteen rooms were opened in the economic part of the temple, and the remains of the hearth were found in most of them.

The walls of the complex have been restored with cotton, the chairs in the rooms and the walls have been repaired with bricks. All rooms are plastered with straw, only two room walls are plastered with plaster. These two ganja rooms are believed to be the shrines of the temple's economic part. Remains of the kiln, ashes, and many animal bones, humus, bowls, half bowls, and pottery fragments were found during the excavation of the kiln chambers at the top of the temple. The surface of the pottery is decorated with

spruce-leaf, disc-like patterns. Barefoot Buddha compensation marks were also placed on the pottery pieces. Fayoztepa, like Dalvarzintepa and Zartepa, is an archeological site built during the Kushan period and is one of the main adjacent cities.

Sufficient information was later collected and studied through religious sites at Qoratepa and Fayoztepa. The cities of the Kushan period of the Surkhandarya oasis were not only administrative and economic centers, but also served as more religious centers. The Buddhist temples in Dalvarzintepa and Fayoztepa have been economically and culturally connecting the states and peoples of the ancient world since the early days of the Kushan Empire. Fayoztepa was devastated by the Sassanid invasions. The end of the 5th century In the 1st half of the 6th century, the ruins of the temple were used by the Hephthalites as a hut. During the Arab conquest, Fayoztepa was completely destroyed and later left under mobile sands. The complex is named in honor of the director of the local museum of local lore RF Fayozov, who made a significant contribution to the study of this architectural monument. In 2003-2006, archaeologists from Japan, Russia, France and Germany visited Surkhandarya to study and excavate ancient monuments such as Termez, Qoratepa, Kampirtepa and Fayoztepa. During the excavations, many years of research were diagnosed. Archaeologists from the leading universities of the country took part in this research. As a result of research on this temple, the expected result was the discovery of a Buddhist temple, a statue of Bodhisattva and other objects in Fayoztepe. Most importantly, the temple occupies a large area, so scholars around the world have recognized it as the best find in Buddhism. Research has shown that Buddhism spread to China, India and Japan. In cooperation with the UNESCO Office in Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Culture of Uzbekistan and the Japanese Research Center, a small sample of the temple found in Fayoztepa was built. This complex is an artistic heritage of Buddhists in Uzbekistan and is known all over the world. Today, Fayoztepa is recognized as an open-air museum and attracts foreign tourists to witness its secrets.

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